

in the values of $\log K_1^{\mu=0}$ and $\log \beta_n^{\mu=0}$ (30°) indicate that the stability of Co^{II} complexes are somewhat higher than Ni^{II} complexes. In the above systems, the values of $\log \beta_n^{\mu=n}$ ($n=0.05, 0.10, 0.15$ and 0.20) were plotted against inverse ionic radii (r^{-1}) at different temperatures. The points corresponding to Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes lie on linear curves and those of Fe^{II} and Co^{II} complexes lie above. Similar trend was observed by plotting the values of $\log \beta_n^{\mu=n}$ ($n=0.05, 0.10, 0.15$ and 0.20) vs second ionisation potential of metal ions. The stability constants of the metal chelates follow the order, $\text{Mn}^{II} < \text{Fe}^{II} > \text{Co}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} < \text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$, which agrees with the Irving-William's¹⁴ natural order, except Co^{II} . The greater stability of Co^{II} complex as compared to Ni^{II} complex may be due to the additional stabilisation acquired by Co^{II} complex due to Jahn-Teller distortion, and the higher oxidation state in the complex¹⁵. A number of workers reported higher stability for cobalt complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁹ as compared to that of nickel. Abnormally high stability in case of ferrous complex may be as a result of the orbital stabilisation and additional resonance energy stabilisation introduced through the ligands carrying an aromatic ring system¹⁴, and the higher oxidation state in the complex. In general, catechol complexes are more stable than pyrogallol complexes, which can be justified on the basis of basicity of the ligand.

The thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated using the standard equations¹⁸. The ΔH values were calculated by plotting the values of $\log K_n$ at different temperatures as a function of $(1/T)$ and equating the gradient of this plot with $-\Delta H/4.57$. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are given in Table 1. Chelates of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are formed spontaneously as is obvious by the negative values of ΔG . The negative values of ΔH ensure that the reaction is exothermic. Positive values of ΔS indicate that entropy is the principal driving force for complex formation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. N. Sawhney, for providing facilities. One of the authors (J.K.N.) is thankful to the Kurukshetra University for award of Fellowship.

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Thermodynamics of Complexation of 2,5-Dihydroxydeoxybenzoin with some Common Cations

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Manuscript received 29 July 1983, revised 18 April
1984, accepted 12 August 1986

IN continuation of our work on complexes of 2-hydroxydeoxybenzoin¹ with Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions, the present study describes the sequestering efficiency of 2,5-dihydroxydeoxybenzoin with the same metal ions. The Calvin-Bjerrum's titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti² has been adopted.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand thermodynamic stability constants have been calculated from the results of titration of the following solutions against standardised carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.214 3 mol dm⁻³; dioxan-water medium 1 : 1 by volume): (i) HClO_4 (4.5 mol m⁻³) + Na_2SO_4 (0.20 mol m⁻³), (ii) HClO_4 (4.5 mol m⁻³) + Na_2SO_4 (0.20 mol m⁻³) + ligand (2.00 mol m⁻³), and (iii) metal sulphate (0.20 mol m⁻³) in HClO_4 (4.5 mol m⁻³) + ligand (2.00 mol m⁻³) each in 20 ml of dioxan-water (1 : 1 by volume) containing NaClO_4 (0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³, respectively) at 298 K. The changes of the thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS associated with the complexation reaction have been evaluated using the temperature coefficient of stability constant and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation from the results at three

temperatures, viz. 293, 298 and 303 K for the solutions containing 0.10 mol dm⁻³ of NaClO₄.

Results and Discussion

The parameters $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL of the complexes examined have been calculated using the standard relations given by Irving and Rossotti². From these,

TABLE 1—PROTON—LIGAND AND METAL—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS (*K*) OF 2,5-DIHYDROXYDEOXYBENZOIN AT 298 K

Cation	log <i>K</i> *				log <i>K</i> ₀
	Ionic Strengths (mol dm ⁻³)				
	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	
H ⁺	11.23	11.15	11.08	11.03	11.45
Fe ³⁺	11.13	11.05	10.97	10.92	11.40
Cu ²⁺	8.83	8.65	8.48	8.40	9.25
Zn ²⁺	7.80	7.67	7.55	7.45	8.20
Cd ²⁺	6.10	5.96	5.87	5.78	6.42

*Pointwise calculation and Bjerrum's half-integral value methods.

of the medium. Plots of log *K*^H or log *K* against $\sqrt{I}$ (*I*=ionic strength) have been drawn and extrapolated to *I* = 0 to get the thermodynamic stability constant values (Table 1).

The stabilities of the complexes show the order, Fe³⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Cd²⁺, which agrees with that of the Irving—William's natural order⁴. Fe³⁺ has greater ionic charge and smaller ionic radius and hence it forms the most stable complex⁵ in the series.

The decrease in the values of stability constants with the increase in temperature (Table 2) indicates that high temperature does not favour the formation of stable complexes. The results (Table 2) show the relative values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS associated with the complexation reactions under study. The ΔH values are all negative while the ΔS values are all positive and, therefore, the resulting ΔG values are all negative. This is the criterion of spontaneity. Further, the ΔG values show the trend Fe³⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Cd²⁺. This also confirms the reported order of stability.

TABLE 2—PROTON—LIGAND AND METAL—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS (*K*) OF 2,5-DIHYDROXYDEOXYBENZOIN AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

I = 0.10 mol dm⁻³

Cation	Log <i>K</i> *			- ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹			- ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	293 K	298 K	303 K	293 K	298 K	303 K		
	H ⁺	11.25	11.15	10.97	63.03	63.58	63.58	47.49
Fe ³⁺	11.15	11.05	10.97	62.49	62.70	63.58	30.60	108.68
Cu ²⁺	8.77	8.65	8.54	49.16	49.32	49.49	39.08	34.28
Zn ²⁺	7.78	7.67	7.57	43.60	43.72	43.89	35.66	27.17
Cd ²⁺	6.04	5.96	5.91	33.86	33.98	34.28	22.11	40.13

*Pointwise calculation and Bjerrum's half-integral value methods.

the log *K*^H and log *K* values for the different conditions have been evaluated by the pointwise calculation and Bjerrum's half-integral value methods. The values thus obtained by the two methods are necessarily consistent with each other (Tables 1 and 2). The calculated values of $\bar{n}_H$ are found to be between 0 and 1. Similarly, the calculated $\bar{n}$ values lie between zero and one, although the metal—ligand mole ratio has been kept at 1 : 10 for getting the maximum possible complexation. Precipitation of metal hydroxides made it impossible to examine the behaviour of metal—ligand complexes other than the 1 : 1 metal—ligand complexes.

The reported log *K*^H and log *K* values show a decrease with increasing ionic strengths of the solutions. This is in agreement with the Debye—Hückel's conclusion³ which states that the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies in inverse proportion to ionic strength

The higher value of ΔS for Fe³⁺ is justified due to its higher charge on the ion which causes the greater association with the donor atoms and hence the higher entropy changes occur⁶.

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